

THE LITERATURE REVIEW OF *DURALABHARISHTAM*

¹*Dr. Supriya Bansode, ²Dr. Shardul Chavan, ³Dr. Anju Sreedharan

¹PG Scholar, Dept. of *Rasashastra* and *Bhaishajya Kalpana* APM's Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Sion, Mumbai.

²Associate Professor, Dept. of *Rasashastra* and *Bhaishajya Kalpana* APM's Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Sion, Mumbai.

³Assistant Professor, Dept. of *Rasashastra* and *Bhaishajya Kalpana* APM's Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Sion, Mumbai.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Supriya Bansode

PG Scholar, Dept. of *Rasashastra*
and *Bhaishajya Kalpana* APM's
Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Sion,
Mumbai.

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ABSTRACT

Duralabharishtam is an important Ayurvedic formulation widely used in the management of various conditions such as *Pandu* (anaemia), *Arsha* (haemorrhoids), *Pleeharoga* (spleen disorders), *Gulma* (abdominal lumps), *Hrudrog* (heart diseases), *Grahani* (malabsorption syndrome), *Shotha* (swelling), *Aruchi* (loss of appetite), *Granthi* (cysts), *Arbuda* (tumours/cancer) and *Kushtha* (skin diseases). Classical Ayurvedic literature mentions eight references of this formulation under two variant names, *Sharkarasav* and *Dwitiya Phalarishtam*. Among these, the formulation described in *Ashtanga Hridayam* is most widely accepted and commonly used in clinical practice and in pharmaceutical preparations. The standard formulation consists of nine ingredients of plant origin. The present study aims to critically review this formulation. Based on the analysis of the pharmacological

properties of its ingredients, it can be inferred that *Duralabharishtam* may be effective in all the above-mentioned indications. Among the five *Pathabheda* of mentioned formulation, there is a need to standardize each *Pathabheda* and clinically evaluate them according to *Phalshruti* for their effective use in practice. Pharmacologically, it supports digestion, metabolism, bowel regulation, and has anti-parasitic and anti-inflammatory effects. It is mainly used in gastro-intestinal and metabolic disorders like *Arsha*, *Grahani*, *Pandu*. Limited

research suggests benefits in conditions such as celiac disease and haemorrhoids, through the evidence is not extensive. Further standardization, quality control, and large-scale clinical studies are needed to validate its efficacy.

KEYWORDS: *Duralabharishtam*, *Arsha*, *Grahani*, *Arbuda*, *Granthi*, *Sandhan Kalpana*, Alcoholic Fermentation.

INTRODUCTION

Duralabharishtam is herbal formulation composed entirely of plant-based ingredients. It is a *Bhaishajya Kalpana* preparation and categorized under *Sandhan Kalpana*, which refers to formulations prepared through the process of *Sandhan* (fermentation), resulting in the formation of *Madya* (alcohol).

In day-to-day Ayurvedic practice, *Duralabharishtam* is commonly prescribed medicine for conditions such as *Arsha* (piles), *Amlapitta* (hyperacidity), *Agnimandhya* (digestive impairment), *Kasa* (cough), *Gulma* (abdominal Lump), and other diseases caused by *Mandagani* (diminished digestive fire).

Since it is a well-known and frequently used formulation by *Vaidyas*, it is important to compile and present all related information and available scientific data in one place. This would help practitioners, students, teachers & researchers gain a comprehensive understanding of this formulation.

The objectives of the present study are to collect and review all available data from classical *Ayurvedic* texts and published research, to analyse the formulation and its ingredients, and to understand the probable mode of action of *Duralabharishtam* in relation to the indications mentioned in classical texts.

AIM

This study aims to gather all available references of *Duralabharishtam* and to analyze them comparatively to understand its composition, method of preparation and indications.

STUDY DESIGN

References related to *Duralabharishtam* were collected from relevant classical Ayurvedic texts and systematically documented. Existing research studies were also reviewed. Sources such as the thesis database, research journals, and online platforms were explored to identify

any prior research conducted on this formulation. All the collected information was carefully analyzed with respect to its ingredients, variations in formulation, and indications.

CLASSICAL REFERENCES OF DURALABHARISHTAM

1. पचेद्दुरालभाप्रस्थं द्रोणेऽणं द्विपलैः सह ।

दन्तीपाठाग्निविजयावासामलकनागरैः ॥

तस्मिन्सिताशतं दद्यात्पादस्थेऽन्यच्च पूर्ववत् ।

लिम्पेत्कुम्भं तु फलिनीकृष्णाचव्याज्यमाक्षिकैः ॥

टिप्पणी - पूर्ववदित्यभ्यारिष्टवर्दिति ज्ञेयम् । सहस्त्रयोगम् ७.३४^[1]

अभ्यारिष्ट फलश्रुती

अस्याभ्यासादरिष्टस्य नश्यन्ति गुदजा द्रुतम् ॥

ग्रहणीपाण्डुहृद्रोगप्लीहगुल्मोदरापहः ।

कुष्ठशोफारुचिंहरो बलवर्णाग्निवर्धनः ॥

सिद्धोऽयमभ्यारिष्टो कामलाश्वित्रनाशनः ।

कृमिग्रन्थ्यर्बुदव्यङ्गं राजयक्ष्मज्वरान्तकृत् ॥ सहस्त्रयोगम् ७.२२^[2]

2. पचेद् दुरालभाप्रस्थं द्रोणेऽपां द्विपलैः सह ।

दन्तीपाठाग्निविजयावासामलकनागरैः ॥

तस्मिन्सिताशतं दद्यात्पादस्थेऽन्यच्च पूर्ववत् ।

लिंपेत्कुम्भं तु फलिनीकृष्णाचव्याज्यमाक्षिकैः ॥

दत्त्वा प्रस्थं च धातक्या स्थापयेद् घृतभाजने ।

पक्षात् सशीलितोऽरिष्टः करोत्यग्निं निहन्ति च ।

गुदजग्रहणीपाण्डुकुष्ठोदरगरज्वरान् ॥

श्वयथुप्लीहहृद्रोगगुल्मयक्ष्मवमीकृमीन् ॥ आ. अ. वि. ३/८^[3]

3. दुरालभायाः प्रस्थः स्याच्चित्रकस्य वृषस्य च ।

पथ्यामलकयोश्चैव पाठाया नागरस्य च ॥

दन्त्याश्चद्विपलान् भागान् जलद्रोणे विपाचयेत् ।

पादावशेषे पूते च सुशीते शर्कराशतम् ॥

प्रक्षिप्य स्थापयेत् कुम्भे मासार्धं घृतभाविते ।

प्रलिप्ते पिप्पलीचव्यप्रियङ्गुक्षौद्र सर्पिषा ।
 तस्य मात्रां पिबेत्काले शार्करस्य यथाबलम् ।
 अर्शोसि ग्रहणीदोषमुदावर्तमरोचकम् ॥
 शकृन्मूत्रानिलोद्गारविबन्धानग्निमार्दवम् ।
 हृद्रोगंपाण्डुरोगं च सर्वमेतेन साधयेत् ॥
 इति द्वितीय फलारिष्टः । च. चि. १४/१५३-१५७^[4]

4. दुरालभाया द्विप्रस्थं प्रस्थमामलकस्य च ।
 मुष्ठी चित्रकदन्त्योर्द्वे प्रत्यग्रं चाभयांशतम् ॥
 चतुद्रोणेऽम्भसः काथ्यं शीतं द्रोणावशेषितम् ।
 गुडस्य द्विशतं पूतं मधुनः कुडवान्वितम् ॥
 तद्वत् प्रियङ्गोः पिप्पल्या विडङ्गानां च चूर्णकम् ।
 कुडवं घृतं कुम्भस्थं पक्षादूर्ध्वं पिबेन्नरः ॥
 ग्रहणीपाण्डुरोगार्शः कुष्ठवीसर्पमेहनुत् ।
 स्वरवर्णकरश्चैव रक्तपित्तकफापहः ॥ ग. नि. ६/६७-७०^[5]

5. दुरालभायाः प्रस्थं च चित्रकस्य वृषस्य च ।
 पथ्यामलकयोश्चैव पाठायानागरस्य च ॥१॥
 दद्याद् द्विपलिकान्भागज्जलद्रोणे विपाचयेत् ।
 पादशेषे रसे पूते सुशीते शर्कराशतम् ॥२॥
 दत्त्वा कुम्भे दृढे स्थाप्यं मासार्धं घृतभाजने ।
 प्रलिप्ते पिप्पलीचव्यप्रियङ्गुमधुसर्पिषा ॥ ३ ॥
 तस्य मात्रां पिबेत्काले शार्करस्य यथाबलम् ।
 अर्शोसि ग्रहणीरोगमुदावर्तमरोचकम् ॥ ४ ॥
 शकृन्मूत्रानिलोद्गारविबन्धानग्निमार्दवम् ।
 हृद्रोगं पाण्डुरोगं स सर्वरोगान्प्रणाशयेत् ॥५॥ यो. र.^[8]

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF *DURALABHARISHTAM*1] INGREDIENTS OF *DURALABHARISHTAM* AS PER *SAHASRAYOGAM*.Table No. 1: Ingredients of *Duralabharishtam* as Per *Sahasrayogam*.^{[1][6]}

SR. NO.	INGREDIENTS	LATIN NAME	PART USED	QUANTITY
KWATHA				
DRAVYA				
1	<i>Duralabha</i>	<i>Fagonia arabica</i>	Roots, Leaves, Flowers, Fruits, Bark	8parts
2	<i>Danti</i>	<i>Baliospermum montanum</i>	Roots	1parts
3	<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>	Roots	1parts
4	<i>Chitrak</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Roots	1parts
5	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Fruit	1parts
6	<i>Vasa</i>	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Leaves	1parts
7	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Fruit	1parts
8	<i>Shunthi</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Roots	1parts
9	<i>Jala</i>	Aqua	-	128parts
MADHURA				
DRAVYA				
10	<i>Sita</i>	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>	-	50parts
LIMPANA				
DRAVYA				
11	<i>Priyangu</i>	<i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i>	Fruit	QS
12	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>	Fruit	QS
13	<i>Makshika</i>	Mel	-	QS
14	<i>Chavya</i>	<i>Piper retrofractum</i>	Fruit	QS
15	<i>Ghrita</i>	Clarified butter	-	QS
PRAKSHEPA				
DRAVYA				
16	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i>	Flower	8parts

Note- Ingredients of *Duralabharishtam* as per C. S. and A. S. are correspond to those listed in *Sahasrayogam* (table no. 1); however, the *Prakshepa Dravya* are not specified in C. S. and A. S. [C. S. – *Charak Samhita*, A. S. -*Ashtanga Sangraha*]

2] INGREDIENTS OF *DURALABHARISHATAM* AS PER *GADANIGRAHA*Table No. 02: Ingredients Of *Duralabharishatam* As Per *Gadanigraha*.^{[5][9]}

SR. NO.	INGREDIENTS	LATIN NAME	PARTS USED	QUANTITY
KWATH				
DRAVYA				
1.	<i>Duralabha</i>	<i>Fagonia arabica</i>	Roots, Leaves, Flowers, Fruits, Bark	16parts
2.	<i>Danti</i>	<i>Baliospermum montanum</i>	Roots	0.5parts
3	<i>Chitrak</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Roots	0.5parts
4	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Fruit	50parts
5	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus embelica</i>	Fruit	8parts
6	<i>Jala</i>	Water	-	512parts
MADHURA				
DRAVYA				

7	<i>Guda</i>	Saccharum officinarum	-	100parts
8	<i>Makshika</i>	Mel	-	2parts
LIMPANA DRAVYA				
9	<i>Ghrita</i>	Clarified butter	-	QS
PRAKSHEPA DRAVYA				
10	<i>Priyangu</i>	Callicarpa macrophylla	Fruit	0.67parts
11	<i>Pippali</i>	Piper longum	Fruit	0.67parts
12	<i>Vidanga</i>	Embelia ribes	Fruit	0.67parts

METHOD OF DURALABHARISHTAM PREPARATION

Raw materials were first identified, and decoction of *Kwath Dravya* (ingredients) was prepared following the standard reference method.

Madhur Dravya (sweetening agents) were then added to the decoction and dissolved thoroughly. A porcelain vessel was internally coated with prescribed *Limpana Dravya* (coating substances).

The vessel was sterilized through *Dhoopan* (fumigation) both before and after the *Limpana* (coating) process. After incorporating the *Prakshepa Dravyas*, the prepared mixture was transferred into the coated vessel. The vessel was then covered with the *Sharava* (earthen lid) and sealed with *Matkapad* (*Multani mitti* -smear cloth).

The sealed vessel was kept in a warm, undisturbed place for a period of fifteen days. Throughout this time the fermentation process was carefully observed. At the end of this period, the *Duralabharishtam* was considered ready. The fermented liquid was then filtered using clean muslin cloth, stored in airtight container, and left to mature further.

Figure No. 1: Flow Chart of *Duralabharishtam* Preparation.

Table No. 3: List of Ingredients of *Duralabharishtam* As Per Different Aacharyas.

Sr. No.	Dravya	Sahasrayogam ^[1]	Charak Samhita ^[4]	Ashtang Hridayam ^[6]	Ashtang sangrah ^[7]	Aasava arishta Vigyan ^[3]	Yoga Ratnakara ^[8]	Gad Nigraha ^[5]	Afi V1 P3 ^[9]
1	<i>Duralabha</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2	<i>Patha</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
3	<i>Haritaki</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	<i>Aamalaki</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5	<i>Vasa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
6	<i>Shunthi</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-

7	Danti	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
8	Chitrak	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
9	Sita	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
10	Guda	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
11	Madhu	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
14	Pippali	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
15	Vidang	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
16	Priyangu	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
17	Dhataki	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-

PROPERTIES OF INGREDIENTS

Table No. 4: Properties of Ingredients.

SR.NO.	DRAVYA	RASA	GUNA	VIRYA	VIPAKA	PRABHAVA
1	Duralabha ^[10]	Madhura, Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura	-
2	Chitrak ^[11]	Katu	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	-
3	Danti ^[12]	Katu	Tikshna, Ushna	Ushna	Katu	-
4	Haritaki ^[13]	Kashayapradhana Panchrasa Lavanavarjita	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Madhura	Tridoshar
5	Aamalaki ^[14]	Amlapradhan Panchrasa Lavanavarjit	Guru, Sheeta	Sheeta	Madhura	-
6	Vasa ^[15]	Tikta, Kashaya	Ruksha, Laghu	Sheeta	Katu	-
7	Patha ^[16]	Tikta	Laghu, Tikshna	Ushna	Katu	-
8	Shunthi ^[17]	Katu	Laghu, Snigdha, Ushna	Ushna	Madhura	-
9	Sharkara ^[18]	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura	Pittashamak
10	Guda ^[19]	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	Ushna	Madhura	Vaatshamak
11	Vidanga ^[20]	Katu	Ruksha, Laghu	Ushna	Katu	-
12	Pippali ^[21]	Katu	Snigdha, Laghu	Anushnsheeta	Madhura	-
13	Priyangu ^[22]	Tikta, Kashaya	Sheeta	Sheeta	Katu	Vaathar

PHALSHRUTI OF DURALABHARISHTAM

Table No. 5: Phalshruti of Duralabharishtam.

SR. NO.	PHALSHRUTI	SAHSRAYOGAM ^[1]	A. A. V. ^[3]	C. S. ^[4]	G. NI. ^[5]	Y. R. ^[8]
1	Arsha	+	+	+	+	+
2	Grahani	+	+	+	+	+
3	Pandu	+	+	+	+	+
4	Hrudroga	+	+	+	-	+
5	Kushtha	+	+	-	+	-
6	Swarvarnkara	-	-	-	+	-
7	Balvarnagnikar	+	-	-	-	-
8	Udara	+	+	-	-	-
9	Jwara	+	+	-	-	-
10	Pheeharoga	+	+	-	-	-

11	<i>Yakshma</i>	+	+	-	-	-
12	<i>Krumi</i>	+	+	-	-	-
13	<i>Granthi</i>	+	-	-	-	-
14	<i>Arbuda</i>	+	-	-	-	-
15	<i>Udawarta</i>	-	-	+	-	+
16	<i>Arochaka</i>	+	-	+	-	+
17	<i>Vibandha- Mala, Mutra, Vaayu, Udgara</i>	-	-	+	-	+
18	<i>Agnimandya</i>	-	-	+	-	+
19	<i>Visrpa</i>	-	-	-	+	-
20	<i>Prameha</i>	-	-	-	+	-
21	<i>Raktpitta</i>	-	-	-	+	-
22	<i>Shwaythu</i>	-	+	-	-	-
23	<i>Gulma</i>	+	+	-	-	-
24	<i>Avami</i>	-	+	-	-	-
25	<i>Shopha</i>	+	-	-	-	-
26	<i>Kamala</i>	+	-	-	-	-
27	<i>Shwitra</i>	+	-	-	-	-
28	<i>Vyanga</i>	+	-	-	-	-
29	<i>Garvishahara</i>	-	+	-	-	-
30	<i>Kaphahar</i>	-	-	-	+	-

[G.NI. -Gadanigraha, A. A. V. - Aasav Arishta Vidnyan]

PREVIOUS RELATED RESEARCH WORK DONE

1. REVIEW ARTICLE RELATED TO DURALABHARISHTAM

Table No. 06: Review Article Related To Duralabharishtam.

Sr. No.	Authors	Title, year, journal	Study model	Key intervention	Outcome
1	Dr Shivani Gupta, Dr Bhopinder Singh ^[23]	A Classical Approach Towards Treatment of <i>Arsha Roga</i> - A Review Article; A World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science; 2017, Vol. 3, Issue 10, 69-73.	Classical Ayurvedic Literature Review	Ayurvedic management of <i>Arsha Roga</i> .	In <i>Sravi Arsha</i> management, as a compound formulation, <i>Duralabharishatam</i> 15-20ml twice daily with an equal amount of water.
2	Sinimol T. P., Emy. S. Surendran, Varsha Sumedhan, Meghna. P.P, V. Subhose ^[24]	A Review on the Probable Mode of Action of: <i>Hinguvachadi Churna</i> (powder)- an ayurvedic formulation with multifaceted action; International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research; March 2021, Vol 9, Issue 3, 94-101.	Literature-Based Pharmacological Analysis	<i>Hinguvachadi churn</i> formulation in <i>Agnimandya</i> .	Clinically, with <i>Dashemani Gana</i> (3–6 g of <i>churna</i> or <i>vati</i>), <i>Duralabharishtam</i> , <i>Abhayarishta</i> , <i>Saptamrut Kashaya</i> , <i>Pippalyasava</i> , or <i>Putikaranjasava</i> are administered as <i>Sahapana</i> , as prescribed by the physician.

2. PHARMACEUTICO-ANALYTICAL STUDY ARTICLE RELATED TO *DURALABHARISHTAM*

Table No. 07: Pharmaceutico-Analytical Study Article Related To *Duralabharishtam*.

Sr. No.	Author	Title, Year, Journal	Study Model	Key Intervention	Outcome
1	Nisarga R.M., Jagadeesha Mayya A., and Dinesh Kumar Mishra ^[25]	Role of Different Containers in <i>Sandhana Kalpana</i> with Reference to <i>Duralabharista</i> ; World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research; Jan 2024 Vol 13 Issue 2 1020-1026 ISSN 2277 7105	Comparative Pharmaceutica l Preparation.	Container effect in <i>Sandhan Kalpana</i> .	Among the 5 different <i>Sandhana Patra</i> , alcohol content was observed to be higher in the ceramic pot (7.85%) and the steel vessel (7.08%).

3. CASE REPORT ARTICLE RELATED TO *DURALABHARISHTAM*

Table No. 08: Case Report Article Related To *Duralabharishtam*.

SR. NO.	AUTHOR	TITLE, YEAR, JOURNAL	STUDY MODEL	KEY INTERVENTION RELATED TO	OUTCOME
1	Dr Aneesh M S ^[26]	Management of Celiac Disease with Ayurvedic Treatment: A Case Report; JETIR; July 2024 Vol 11 Issue 7 100-103.	Single Patient Clinical Study	Ayurvedic Management of Celiac Disease	In Celiac disease management for loss of appetite, chronic abdominal pain, <i>Duralabharishtam</i> with <i>Dhanwantharam Gulika</i> -10ml-after lunch twice daily is used.

REFERENCES OF *DURALABHARISHTAM* FROM DIFFERENT TEXTS WITH REMARK

Table no. 09 – References of *Duralabharishtam* From Different Texts With Remark.

Sr. No.	Granthadhar	Shloka Similar To Other Grantha	Rogadhikara	Remark
1	<i>Sahasrayogam</i> 7.34	1] A.S. 2] A.H.	<i>Arsha</i>	1] <i>Sahasrayogam</i> - ➤ टिप्पणी – पूर्ववदित्यभयारिष्टवर्दिति ज्ञेयम् । This text discusses <i>Prakshepa Dravya</i> and <i>Phalshruti</i> [therapeutic benefits] of the <i>Kalpa</i> [formulation]. ➤ The reference is sourced from <i>Ashtaga Hridayam</i> . ➤ <i>Limpan</i> of <i>Sandhan Patra</i> – <i>Ghrita</i> , <i>Phalini</i> , <i>Pippali</i> , <i>Chavya</i> , <i>Madhu</i> . 2] A.S. - ➤ The same <i>Shloka</i> [verse] is included, with only minor variations in the wording. ➤ The <i>Phalshruti</i> is not mentioned in this verse.

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabharishth.</u> ➤ The specific line टिप्पणी - पूर्वदित्यभयारिष्टवर्दिति ज्ञेयम् । is absent from this text, unlike in the <i>Sahasrayogam</i>. 3] A.H. – ➤ <i>Phalshruti</i> is not mentioned in this text. ➤ The <i>Prakshepa Dravya</i> mentioned in A. H. <i>Vaktvya</i> by <i>Arundatta</i> and in <i>Abhayarishth</i> is <i>Dhataki Pushpa</i>. ➤ The explanatory line: टिप्पणी - पूर्वदित्यभयारिष्टवर्दिति ज्ञेयम् । is not present. ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabharishth.</u>
2	<i>Charak Samhita</i>	<p>1] A.A.V. - <i>Duralabharishtha</i> 3/7^[27]</p> <p>2] B. B. R.- <i>Duralabharishthah</i> (1)^[28]</p>	<i>Arsha</i>	<p>1] C.S. -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Dwitiya Phalarishthah.</u> ➤ <i>Prakshepa Dravya</i> are not explicitly mentioned. ➤ <i>Limpan</i> of <i>Sandhan Patra – Ghrita, Pippali, Chavya, Madhu, Priyangu</i>. <p>2] A.A.V.-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Dulalabharishtha.</u> <p>3] B. B. R.-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabharishthah.</u>
3	<i>Gadnigrah</i>	<p>1] A.F.I.</p> <p>2] B.B.R.- <i>Dulalabhasav</i>^[29]</p> <p>3] <i>Sahasrayogam</i> 7.35^[30]</p> <p>4] A.A.V. – <i>Dulalabhasav</i> 9/2^[31]</p>	<i>Grahani</i>	<p>1] G. NI. -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Priyangu, Pippali, and Vidanga</i> are listed as <i>Prakshepa Dravya</i>. ➤ The <i>Rogadhikara</i> are mentioned in a separate table no. 5 ➤ <i>The Matra</i> of <i>Dravya</i> is detailed in the subsequent table no.02 ➤ <i>Limpan</i> of <i>Sandhan Patra – Ghrita</i>. <p>2] A.F.I.-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ <i>Shloka</i> and <i>Phalshruti</i> - same as that of G. NI. ➤ Reference source: Taken from <i>Gadanigrah</i>. ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabharista.</u> <p>3] B.B.R.-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabhasav.</u> <p>4] A.A.V. –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabhasav.</u>
4	<i>Y.R.-</i>	-	<i>Arsha</i>	<p>1] Y.R.-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Sharkarasav.</u> ➤ <i>Danti</i> has been omitted from the content.
5	<i>A.A.V.</i>	<p>1] B.B.R. - <i>Duralabharishthah</i> (2)^[32]</p>	<i>Arsha</i>	<p>1] A.A.V. -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The explanatory line:

				<p>टिप्पणी - पूर्ववदित्यभयारिष्टवर्दिति ज्ञेयम् is not present in this text's version.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabhasav.</u> ➤ The <i>Phalshruti</i> of the <i>Kalpa</i> is mentioned table no.5 <p>2] B.B.R. –</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The formulation is referred to as <u>Duralabharishtah.</u> ➤ The reference is taken from A. A. V. 3/8.
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[Y.R.- Yogaratnakara]

CONCLUSION

This review emphasizes the classical relevance and pharmacological importance of *Duralabharishtam*, a widely used formulation under *Sandhana Kalpana* in Ayurvedic practice. The study shows that *Duralabharishtam* is mentioned in several classical texts such as *Sahasrayogam*, *Ashtanga Hridayam*, *Charak Samhita*, *Gadanigraha* and *Yogaratanakara*, reflecting its long-standing therapeutic value. Although there are minor variations in the ingredients across these texts, the core composition remains largely the same, with key ingredients including *Duralabha*, *Haritaki*, *Amalaki*, *Chitrak*, and *Danti*.

A comparative evaluation of different formulations indicates that the version described in *Ashtanga Hridayam* is most widely followed in clinical practice. Variations in the inclusion or exclusion of *Prakshepa Dravya* (e.g., *Dhataki*, *Pippali*, *Vidanga*, and *Priyangu*), *Limpan Dravya* (e.g., *Ghrita*, *Pippali*, *Chavya*, *Madhu*, *Priyangu*, and *Phalini*), and different sweetening agents (*Sharkara*, *Guda* and *Madhu*), may influence both therapeutic efficacy and the fermentation process. The use of *Dhataki Pushpa* is particularly significant, as it facilitates natural fermentation and improves the bioavailability of active constituents.

Based on pharmacological properties (*Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya*, and *Vipaka*) of its ingredients, *Duralabharishtam* is believed to have actions such as *Deepana* (enhancing digestive fire), *Pachana* (digestive), *Anulomana* (regulating bowel movement), *Krimighna* (antiparasitic), and *Shothahara* (anti-inflammatory). Ingredients like *Chitraka*, *Pippali*, and *Shunthi* help improve digestion and metabolism, while *Haritaki* and *Amalaki* balance *Tridosha*. This combination explains its wide range of uses in conditions such as *Arsha*, *Grahani*, *Pandu*, *Gulma*, and *Kushtha*. Classical ayurvedic texts describe five different *Pathbheda* (variants) of this formulation.

Analysis based on disease indications (*Rogaghnta*) suggests that *Duralabharishtam* is mainly

useful in gastrointestinal and metabolic disorders, especially those related to *Mandagni* (impaired digestion). Its effectiveness in conditions like *Arsha* (haemorrhoids) and *Grahani* (malabsorption syndrome) is likely due to its ability to improve digestion and regulate bowel function. Its use in systemic conditions such as *Hrudroga*, *Shotha*, and *Granthi* indicates broader therapeutic potential.

A review of existing research shows that scientific studies on this formulation are limited but meaningful. Pharmaceutical studies suggest that factors such as the fermentation process and the type of container can influence alcohol content, which may affect the potency of the formulation. Clinical evidence, although limited, indicates potential benefits in conditions such as celiac disease and *Arsha* when used as part of combined therapy. However, the lack of large-scale clinical trials remains a significant limitation.

Despite its classical importance and widespread use, there is a clear need for standardization, quality control, and further scientific validation. Variations in composition across classical texts and commercial preparations may lead to inconsistent therapeutic outcomes. Well-structured experimental and clinical studies are required to establish its efficacy, safety, and mechanism of action within an evidence-based framework. Further research is essential to validate its clinical effectiveness and support its integration into modern healthcare practice.

NEED FOR STUDY

1. To ensure regulatory compliance required for establishing a pharmacopeial standard.
2. To provide therapeutic validation through limited clinical evidence of efficacy.

SCOPE OF STUDY

Of all available *Pathbheda* –

1. Standardization of the pharmaceutical preparation.
2. Analysis of physicochemical properties.
3. Evaluation of phytochemical profile.
4. Determination of shelf-life.
5. Assessment of therapeutic effectiveness, including:
 - a. Clinical evaluation for the indicated disorder.
 - b. Assessment of safety and efficacy.

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